

ELEMENTAL ANALYSIS OF SILYBUM MARIANUM (L. GAERTNER) FRUIT DRY EXTRACT

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Abstract. Silybum marianum (L.) Gaerth. (Asteraceae) - a valuable medicinal plant The following pharmacological properties of dosage forms from Silybum marianum are described in domestic and foreign literature: antioxidant, antitoxic, hemostatic, hepatoprotective, detoxifying, choleric, anti-inflammatory, wound healing, reparative, laxatives, tonic, cholagogue, tonic, cholagogue, choleric. Milk thistle fruit has been used to treat a range of diseases for over 2,000 years. It is widely used in practice as a hepatoprotector, especially in liver diseases. Currently, the introduction of a number of effective methods that provide a fast and high level of accuracy in trace element analysis has opened up a wide range of possibilities in this regard.

Key words: Macro and micro elements, mass spectrometry, analysis, quantity, dry extract, milk thistle, medicine.

The aim of the study: The purpose of this work is the analysis of the elemental composition of dry extract of the fruit of milk thistle Silybum marianum (L. Gaertner)

Method of quantitative determination of micro- and macroelements by induction mass spectrometry with conjugate plasma. Apparatus and instruments used: A similar mass spectrometer. Microwave decomposition device (Germany).

Results: In Uzbekistan, the development of products of functional and therapeutic and prophylactic purposes is underway to prevent various diseases and enhance the protective functions of the body, reduce the risk of exposure to harmful substances, including for the population living in ecologically unfavorable zones. The analysis results are presented in the table below (table 1).

Table 1

Name of macro and microelements	Quantity, mg / kg	Name of macro and microelements	Quantity, mg / kg
Li7	0.201	K 39	9469.416
Be 9	0.034	Ca 42	6620.220
B 11	44.421	Ti 48	8.891

It was found that the extract of milk thistle fruit contains little toxic elements of lead, cadmium, beryllium, mercury and thallium, and their content complies with the sanitary norms and standards No. 0283.

Conclusions: Dry extract of milk thistle fruit contains an optimal amount of flavolignans, amino acids, carbohydrates, proteins and vitamins, as well as trace elements Beryllium, Lithium, potassium, calcium, titanium. Based on the results obtained, the expediency of including dry extract of milk thistle in medicinal products and biologically active food additives was determined.

References:

1. Hadolin M, Skerget M, Knez Z, Bauman D. (2001). High pressure extraction of vitamin E-rich oil from *Silybum marianum*. *Food Chem* 74: pp 355–364.
2. Jeffrey, C. (2007). *Compositae: introduction with key to tribes*. In Kadereit, J.W., Jeffrey, C. (Eds.), *Families and Genera of Vascular Plants, vol. VIII: Flowering Plants, Eudicots, Asterales*. Springer-Verlag, Berlin, Germany, pp. 61–87.
3. Parry JW, Cheng Z, Moore J, Yu LL. (2008). Fatty acid, antioxidant and antiproliferative capacity of selected cold-pressed seed flours. *J. Am.Oil Chem. Soc.*, 85(5): pp 457-464.